

Identifying the “hands” (and the “ears”) of the Mesopotamian *lilissu*-kettledrum

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1. Introduction

This paper will study some hands (ŠU.MIN = *qātā*) related to the Mesopotamian cultic kettledrum often called *lilissu* in Akkadian. They are mentioned in these lines from the obverse of TU 47,¹ a Late Babylonian tablet from the city of Uruk that preserves a cultic commentary of the ritual to cover the *lilissu* with its drumhead:²

16 ŠU.MIN.MEŠ *ša*₂ ina LI.LI.IS^{zabar} ŠUB-u₂ MU-ši-na ana MU-ar₂ SAĜ-šu^dZI.ŠUM₂.MU
17 KIN.KIN.NA^dBI.ĠIRI₃-GID₂.DA *Taḥ-ḥu-u*₂^dŠEG₉.BAR-IM₂.IM₂.ME IN DI AŠ^dUR₃.BAD₃.DA
18 *Ne₂-re-bi*^dUR₃.BAD₃.DA-ḤUM.ḤUM *Ub-ba-lu-u*₂(-)^dKUR-du *ub-ba-lu-u*₂
^dGUB.BA.<GA.RA.RA.E₃>. {MEŠ}
19 IN DI AŠ(-)^dKUR-SILIM-ti^dA.BA.RA.LAḤ₅ ŠUDU₃ MES ŠU.MIN.MEŠ DIRI.GA ana
^dŠAR₂.UR u^dŠAR₂.GAZ
20 ^{he-pi2} *r*PAP-šu₂-nu^r DIŠ DA-ra-AZ SU^{he-pi2}

16 The hands that are placed in the kettledrum. (This is) to mention their names: Rēšu (is)
17 Zišumu. Kinkinna (is) Biḡiri-gida. Taḥḥû (is) Šegbar-imime. ... (is) Urbada. Nērebi
18 (is) Urbada-ḥumḥum. Ubbalû(-)ikaššādû ... (is) Gubba<garara'e>
19 ... (-)Kašād-šalimti (is) Abaralah ... The extra hands (stand) for Šarur and Šargaz.
20 ^{broken off} their entirety ... ^{broken off}

Identifying these “hands” has divided the Assyriological community, which has proposed four identifications for them: handles, tuning bolts, drumsticks, and ritual objects placed inside the *lilissu*.³ To put an order in this debate, the present article will assess each proposal from a philological perspective, but also by making recourse to some of the very few extant depictions of *lilissu*-kettledrums. Comparisons with other ritual drums from past and modern cultures worldwide will also be established to evaluate each identification and, eventually, to shed new light on the nature and function of these “hands.”

2. The “hands” (and “ears”) of the *lilissu* as handles

This identification was proposed by Livingstone, *Mystical and Mythological Explanatory Works* (1986), 191, 202–203, and multiple scholars have accepted it since.⁴ In its favor, it may be argued the Sumerian šu and the Akkadian *qātu* may mean “handle”⁵ in addition to “hand.” Furthermore, kettledrums usually have lifting handles.⁶ However, TU 47: obv.

¹ Abbreviations for cuneiform texts follow the *Reallexikon der Assyriologie*.

² TU 47 appears here in the CAMS/GKAB edition supplied with some points from Gabbay, *Pacifying the Hearts* (2014), 130 n. 459. However, my translation follows rather the translation of Livingstone, *Mystical and Mythological Explanatory Works* (1986), 191, 202–203.

³ Livingstone, *Mystical and Mythological Explanatory Works* (1986), 191, 202–203; Gabbay, *Pacifying the Hearts* (2014), 120, 129–30; Helle, “Role of Authors” (2018): 233; and Borrelli and Escobar “Crafting Purity” (2022): 64 n. 132, respectively.

⁴ Focke, “Die Göttin Ninimma” (1999–2000): 103; Krebernik, “Šegbar(a)imim(e)” (2009–2011): 345; Franklin, *Kinyras* (2015), 24; Koubková, *Washing the mouth* (2016), 38.

⁵ CAD Q *qātu* 3 and ePSD2. Handles of copper (^{ur}dušū) and bronze (šuzabar) are respectively known in the Ur III texts MVN 3, 152: obv. 7 and CDLJ 2012-1 §5.06: obv. 5', but they are not related to a *lilissu*.

⁶ Jackowski, “Traditional Custom of Kettledrumming” (2006), fig. 2.

16–20 speaks of nine “hands” per *lilissu*, whereas the impression of a Seleucid seal from Uruk belonging to Anu-iqīšannu shows the following (see Figure 1):

FIG. 1

Figure 1. My drawing of BRM 2, 3 (= MLC 2103): top edge, rightmost impression, according to its photo in <https://www.ebl.lmu.de/f7903171-fc8b-4a52-b9a1-e16dc899f3cb>

Here, and in a second seal of Anu-iqīšannu⁷ a person (perhaps a *kalû*) beats a kettledrum with two (visible)⁸ handles. The present situation speaks against an identification of the “hands” of the *lilissu* as lifting handles.

An allusion to the handles of the *lilissu* could be found in these lines from the obverse of BagM Beih. 2, 89, a Late Babylonian duplicate of the *Uruk List of Kings and Sages*:⁹

9 [d15 iš]-r tu' AN-e ana E₂.AN.NA u₂-še-ri-du BALAG^{zabar}
10 [ša₂] ĜEŠTU[?].MIN[?].MEŠ-šu₂ ^{na4}ZA.GIN₃.NA ina ši-pir ^dNIN-A₂.GAL

9 He made [Ištar] descend [fr]om the heaven to the Eanna temple. A bronze *balaggu*
10 [who]se ears (are made) of lapis lazuli (was made) following Nin-Agal's instructions.

This excerpt mentions a pair (MIN) of lapis lazuli objects belonging to a kettledrum, here called *balaggu*, and not *lilissu*, to highlight its ritual character.¹⁰ Drawing on TU 47: obv. 16–20, the cuneiform signs that spell the name of these precious objects were firstly read r'ŠU[?].MIN[?].MEŠ “hands.”¹¹ However, Helle, *First Authors* (2020), 360, 362 has recently read them ĜEŠTU[?].MIN[?].MEŠ “ears,” given an unpublished duplicate of the *Uruk List of Kings and Sages* with a well-preserved ĜEŠTU in the place of supposed ŠU.¹²

There are anthropomorphic drums, whose body represents a human head including ears.¹³ However, cuneiform excerpts comparing the *lilissu* with the head of a deity (arguably having ears) are missing.¹⁴ When looking for another identification for the “ears” of the *lilissu*, one already finds proposals to identify them as handles.¹⁵ I think this is a plausible identification, but previous proposals in that sense have appeared without arguments to support it. As a result, I will present now my arguments to identify ĜEŠTU.MIN.MEŠ

⁷ Wallenfels, *Uruk. Hellenistic Seal Impressions* (1994), no. 52. Extant impressions are not neat enough to assess the reconstruction of this seal made by Wallenfels therein.

⁸ *Ibid.* no. 51 reconstructs a kettledrum with two handles. Nevertheless, a closer look at BRM 2, 3: top edge, rightmost impression, perhaps the neatest impression of this seal, shows one of the handles in the center of the kettle, and not in one of its extremes (*pace* Wallenfels), as shown by my drawing. This suggests a drum with four handles, each one occupying a quarter of a circle. Boehmer, “Ein frühnächtliches Fest” (2014): 128 identifies a cauldron with two handles on an Uruk-III seal with a kettledrum. However, the drum should be portrayed next to a musician as in Delougaz and Kantor, *Chogha Mish I* (1996), plate 155a.

⁹ Edition: Helle, “Role of Authors” (2018): 233.

¹⁰ About the links between *balaggu* and *lilissu*, see Gabbay, “Balaĝ Instrument” (2014), 135–136.

¹¹ Gabbay, *Pacifying the Hearts* (2014), 119 n. 370; Annus, *Overturned Boat* (2016), 27.

¹² Jiménez, “Young Anu-bēlšunu” (forthcoming) will publish this tablet. The editor has allowed me to cite the beginning of obv. 4 here: [ša₂] ĜEŠTU.MIN-šu₂ ^{na4}ZA.GIN₃.NA.

¹³ This is the case, for instance, of two anthropomorphic, cultic drums from 19th-century Congo currently preserved in the *Ethnologisches Museum Berlin*: III C 1962 (<https://recherche.smb.museum/detail/212054/bechertrommel>) and III C 2672 (<https://recherche.smb.museum/detail/212443/zyindertrommel>). Thanks to Evelyn Koubková for communicating their existence to me.

¹⁴ At most, SAA 3 39: obv. 11 compares the *lilissu* with the heart of a deity.

¹⁵ Helle, *First Authors* (2020), 360, 362.

with handles, probably to be used by the *kalû*-priest to lift the *lilissu* and change its location during a procession.¹⁶ My first argument is that this identification aligns with the Late Babylonian seal impression showing a kettledrum with, at least, a pair of handles (Figure 1). As my second argument, the Akkadian *uznu*, a usual reading of the Sumerogram $\hat{G}\hat{E}\hat{S}T\hat{U}$, denotes a vase/pot handle, not only an ear.¹⁷ This is interesting since a Sumerian translation of the *lilissu* presents this sound tool as a cauldron (^{urudu}šen) sitting over a stand ($\hat{h}ur-sa\hat{g}$, literally “mountain”).¹⁸

Against this identification of $\hat{G}\hat{E}\hat{S}T\hat{U}.MIN.ME\hat{S}$ stands $\hat{g}\hat{e}\hat{s}tu\ za_3-mi_2$ (“ear of the za_3-mi_2 ”) = *hasīs sammī* (“opening of the *sammū*”). Found in some lexical texts,¹⁹ this expression is often understood as the designation of a²⁰ hole carved on the sound box²¹ of the *sammū*-chordophone to increase its resonance.²² However, with its dual form (MIN), $\hat{G}\hat{E}\hat{S}T\hat{U}.MIN.ME\hat{S}$ suggests at least, two objects (or a pair number of them). Kettledrums have, at most, a single hole on their bottom to equalize the air pressure inside and out of the kettle, allowing the drum to resonate.²³ Note further that the “ears” of the *lilissu* would be made of a material (lapis lazuli) different from the material of the kettle (bronze), while the equalization hole in the kettledrums would be drilled through the metal of the kettle.

To sum up, $\hat{G}\hat{E}\hat{S}T\hat{U}.MIN.ME\hat{S}$ in the *Uruk List of Kings and Sages* would denote two handles to lift the *lilissu*. On a cross-cultural level, this would recall the Chinese *ěr* (耳) “ear,” which also describes some lifting attachments to be found in the bell-like sound tool *chúnyú* (鐃干). This may be relevant, as the *lilissu* and the *chúnyú* might be roughly contemporary sound tools. Indeed, the *chúnyú* was mainly used from the Spring and Autumn Period (ca. 770–481 BCE) to the Eastern Han Dynasty (ca. 25–220 CE).²⁴

3. The “hands” of the *lilissu* as tuning bolts

Considering the functioning of the Early Modern European *timpani* and their tuning bolts, Gabbay, *Pacifying the Hearts* (2014), 120, 129 (n. 458–459) suggested that the “hands” of the *lilissu* could stand for tuning bolts.²⁵ It is worth comparing the *lilissu* with the Early Modern European *timpani*, among others, since *timpani* were used in sacred, and not only

¹⁶ About the lifting of the *lilissu* in the course of a procession, see Gabbay, *Pacifying the Hearts* (2014), 123, 171, in addition to the texts *JCS* 70, 189–227, rev. iii 15' and *Akkadica* 144-2, obv. 4'.

¹⁷ CAD, U-W *uznu* 5 (handle). For archaeological remains of Babylonian bronze cauldrons with handles, see Braun-Holzinger, “Bronze Objects from Babylonia” (1988), 119, 121, and 130 n. 1.

¹⁸ Mur-gu₄ = *imrū* = *ballu*, A II 192 and *Nebuchadnezzar* I 9 (= RIMB 2, 4.9), 38–39).

¹⁹ CUSAS 12, 3.1.1: b iv 7; RA 19, 149: rev. ii 3'; OrNS 29, 275–278: obv. 6; MCT 132, Ud: rev. 17.

²⁰ Emar 6-1, p. 240: r ii 17 (*ha-si₂-sa₃ sa₃-am-me₂-e*) may refer to two holes (*hasīsā sammē*, in dual).

²¹ As suggested by $\hat{g}\hat{e}\hat{s}\hat{t}u\ za_3-mi_2$ (“wooden ear of the za_3-mi_2 ”) in CUSAS 12, 3.1.1.: b iv 7.

²² Lawergren and Gurney, “Sound Holes” (1987): 39–40. I would also include here the $\hat{G}\hat{E}\hat{S}T\hat{U}.MIN.ME\hat{S}$ of the *tibbu* 'u-instrument in KAR 90: rev. 17. MacGinnis, “Shalmaneser III and the Harp” (2019), 83 recently identified them with handles, although he also said that said handles would allow “the musicians to strap the harp to their waists, thus leaving both hands free as depicted on the reliefs.” However, a handle is something to be held with a hand. Following Meinhold, *Ištar in Aššur* (2009), which amended KAR 90: rev. 17 with *ina* “in, on” (i.e., *an'-ša-ab-ta* KU₃.SIG₁₇ *ša-ri-ri iš-ku-nu* <*ina*> $\hat{G}\hat{E}\hat{S}T\hat{U}.MIN.ME\hat{S}$ -*ša₂* “two rings of shining gold were placed on its ears”), I would identify $\hat{G}\hat{E}\hat{S}T\hat{U}.MIN.ME\hat{S}$ in KAR 90: rev. 17 as sound holes (like those of the *sammū*) to be protected with rings (*ansabtu*). On a cross-cultural level, the resonance holes of the Calabrese chordophone called *chitarra battente* are also called *orecchie* “ears” (Tucci and Ricci, “The Chitarra Battente in Calabria” (1985): 83–84).

²³ Packer, *Acoustics of the Orchestral Kettledrum* (1993), 9, 24, 28. See also the 19th-century kettledrum from Sudan cataloged by the British Museum as 2012, 2048.1 (https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/E_2012-2048-1 and <https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/image/1358828001>).

²⁴ Jao, *Harmoniousness* (2022), 149–150, 204.

²⁵ A proposal followed by Borrelli and Escobar, “Crafting Purity” (2022): 64 n. 132.

court, music.²⁶ However, as suggested by Figure 2, the tuning bolts on the Early Modern European *timpani* form a crown over the head. Such “crown” is not seen in Mesopotamian kettledrums, as inferable by seeing Figure 1 in this paper.²⁷

FIG. 2

Figure 2. Two kettledrums with their tuning bolts (and drumsticks). Source: Virdung, *Musica getuscht* (1511), 25 ([https://imslp.org/wiki/Musica_getuscht_\(Virdung,_Sebastian\)](https://imslp.org/wiki/Musica_getuscht_(Virdung,_Sebastian)))

More importantly, an identification of the “hands” of the *lilissu* with tuning bolts may overlook the fact that the *kalû*-priest mainly fastened the drumhead directly to the kettle²⁸ with wooden pegs (Ĝ^{es} GAG.MEŠ) soaked (*šapû*) in glue (ŠE.ĜIN₂) and interconnected with the sinew from the (bull's) left thigh (SA^uz^u ĜEŠ^u.KUN GUB₃).²⁹ The possibilities for moving the pegs to tune the *lilissu* would become severely restricted because of the glue on the pegs.³⁰ Moreover, since the pegs would be bound together,³¹ it would be more difficult to change the place of a single peg without unintentionally moving the others.

There was probably no need to re-tune the *lilissu* once it was finished. Unlike the Early European *timpani*, which had to be re-tuned to play within an orchestra, the *lilissu* would never play with other melodic instruments (e.g., harps, pipes, etc.), with which common pitches had to be established. Moreover, the drumhead of the *lilissu* was made of leather (= tanned hide), which is less sensitive to weathering than rawhide (usual material of a drumhead).³² This lesser sensibility would reduce the loosening of the drumhead of the *lilissu* due to cold weather or an increase in humidity.

Moreover, there are many non-tunable kettledrums, such as the Moroccan *tam-tam* (colloquially called *tibilāt*, طيبالات, “small drums”).³³ The coverings for this pair of small drums, made of a thick rawhide (e.g., camel hide), are glued and fastened to the kettle with glued rawhide laces.³⁴ These factors make it unnecessary to retune the *tam-tam*, other than to warm their head when they become loose (losing their vibration) due to cold.

²⁶ According to a link (<https://www.viii.org/timpani-oratorios-works>), there are 68 Early Modern pieces of sacred music featuring *timpani* from J. S. Bach (1685–1750) to F. J. Haydn (1732–1809) and W. A. Mozart (1756–1791). For the use of *timpani* in Early Modern court music, see Bowles, “Timpani and Their Performance” (1997): 192, 194, and 197.

²⁷ See also CBCY 5, 26.7 (and 51.6) and TU 47 (reverse), but the latter is an uncovered kettledrum.

²⁸ If the lexical entry Ĝ^{es} gur₂ balaĝ = *kippat balaggi* “wooden hoop of the *balaggu*” (Ur₅-ra = *hubullu* VI: 106; Emar 6-2, p. 508-515+: obv. ii 46–47) refers to the *lilissu* (as argued by Gabbay, *Pacifying the Hearts* (2014), 119), it could describe the *wooden rim* formed by the pegs, and not a proper wooden rim. Otherwise, the mention of the pegs outside the lexical evidence could not be explained.

²⁹ BagM Beih. 2, 5: rev. 12–13; KAR 60: rev. 9–11; TU 44: obv. i 30–31. See Mirelman, “Drum construction in the *lilissu* ritual” (2010): 50–51 and Tudeau, *Building in Assyria* (2019), 84.

³⁰ Cf. Rattray, *Ashanti* (1923), 259 about the drums of Asante people (central Ghana).

³¹ This means that the lace could stretch and tune the drumhead only indirectly.

³² Mirelman, “Drum Construction in the *lilissu* Ritual” (2010): 50–51. Some drums have a head made of leather instead of rawhide, such as the Iroquois water drum (Dean, *Drum* (2012), 72). According to Kilmer, “Pauke und Trommel” (2003–2005): 369, the leather would be for a protective cover. However, in addition to the comments by Gabbay, *Pacifying the Hearts* (2014), 120, the fastening with pegs and laces occurs after the covering of the *lilissu* with the leather, so there is no rawhide drumhead. According to van Driel, “Ancient Skin Processing” (2002), 258, a drumhead made of leather obtained with fats (as would partially be the case of the *lilissu*) would be functional, as it is stiff enough to stand the drummer's beating.

³³ See https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Tbilat_Marokko2.jpg for a photo.

³⁴ Thanks to the Moroccan musicians Amin Chaachoo and Said Lahlou for these orientations.

4. The “hands” of the *lilissu* as drumsticks

In addition to handles, Helle, “Role of Authors” (2018): 233 suggested that the “hands” of the *lilissu* could be a group of drumsticks. In favor of this proposal, European kettle-drummers have usually had various types of sticks and mallets to produce different sounds on their drums, according to the musical needs of the repertoire.³⁵ However, TU 47: obv. 16–20 says that the *lilissu* had nine “hands.” If they denoted drumsticks, one might expect to find an allusion to an even number of “hands” (i.e., pairs of drumsticks). Furthermore, as has happened with other attempts at finding Sumerian or Akkadian terms for drumsticks,³⁶ Helle’s proposal does not fit with the Mesopotamian iconographic record, which never shows drums played with sticks.³⁷ Thus, the *lilissu* may be compared, among others, with the *duggī/bāyā*, a modern Northern Indian kettledrum played with the hands.³⁸

5. The “hands” as figurines placed inside the *lilissu*

Some translations of ŠU.MIN.MEŠ ša₂ ina LI.LI.IS^{zabar} ŠUB-u₂ in TU 47: obv. 16 (translated as “The hands that are placed in the kettledrum” at the beginning of this article) understand that the hands were placed/thrown (ŠUB-u₂) inside (*ina*) the *lilissu*.³⁹ This has been seen as unlikely on various occasions, which explains the existence of translations⁴⁰ and interpretations⁴¹ of this chain suggesting instead that the “hands” were laid on the top of the *lilissu*. However, the identification of these “hands” as objects put inside the kettle of this drum may be likely for various philological, in addition to cross-cultural⁴² reasons.

The first philological argument for this identification is that the prescriptions to put objects inside the *lilissu* are not followed by instructions for taking them out later. The text IV R², 23-1+: obv. i 6–7 reads 12 DIĠIR.MEŠ ZABAR a-na ŠA₃ LILIS^{zabar} ŠUB-ma /

³⁵ Bowles, “Double Beat of the Thundering Drum” (1991): 424.

³⁶ This is the case of Wiggermann, *Mesopotamian Protective Spirits* (1992), 16–17, which translated *tirka* in the text *Šēp lemutti ina bīt amēli*, 253 (7 KUŠ.GU₄.GAL *tir-ka* LILIS^{zabar}) as “drumstick.” However, a dual *tirkā* (perhaps to be written *tir-ka-a*) would be preferable. Following AHw T *te/irku*, CAD, T *tirku* b, and Rendu Loisel, *Bruit et Émotion* (2011), 84 n. 312, I parse *tir-ka* as a non-standard spelling of the construct form of *tirku* “beat” (cf. *ti-rik a-le-e* “the beat of the *alū*-drums” in the text BWL 204: col. A 9).

³⁷ Some old reconstructions of Ur-Nammâ’s stela depict drumsticks for playing the a₂-la₂/*alū* giant frame drums (Rashid, *Mesopotamien* (1984) 72 (Text illustration) and 73 (fig. 54). However, said sticks is cannot be seen in the most recent reconstruction of this stela and images of the different fragments (Canby, “*Ur-Nammu*” *Stela* (2001), plates 9, 11–12, and 38–40).

³⁸ Dick, “*Duggī* [*dugdugī*, *dugdugā*, *daggā*]” (2016).

³⁹ Thureau-Dangin, “Un acte de donation” (1919): 152, “Les « mains » qui se trouvent dans le *lilissu* d’airain.” CAMS/GKAB, “the hands that are thrown in the bronze kettledrum.”

⁴⁰ Livingstone, *Mystical and Mythological Explanatory Works* (1986), 191 (“the hands laid in the bronze kettledrum”).

⁴¹ Gabbay, *Pacifying the Hearts* (2014), 129.

⁴² Borrelli and Escobar, “Crafting Purity” (2022): 64 n. 132 referred to the fact that various cultures around the world fill the body of their ritual drums with objects, but no example or reference was provided. I could find different cases of drums filled with ritual objects in these references: Roscoe, *Northern Bantu* (1915), 87–88 and *Bakitara* (1923), 231; Blades, *Percussion instruments* (1984), 57–58; Feld, “Sound as Symbolic System” (1986), 151–153; Le Roux, “*Ngoma Lungundu*” (2009): 106; Rees, “Membrane Drums” (2013), 195–196; Pérez de Arce, *Instrumentos sonoros de Sudamérica* (2021), 372. I will add two further examples. On the one hand, according to *Sud.* τ.1164 (= τύμπανα; edition: *Suda Online: Byzantine Lexicography*; thanks to Kamila Wyśłucha for this reference), the Indian kettledrums had many (πολλοί), large (μεγάλοι) brass bells (κόδωνας ὀρειχάλκου) inside (ἐς αὐτὸν). Moreover, since the 17th century CE, jingles and chickpeas have also been thrown into the *adufe*, an Iberian square frame drum used in Catholic festivities (Molina, *Frame Drums* (2010), 144). A woman throws both things into an *adufe* between minutes 7:14 and 7:34 of this ethnographic reportage in Spanish (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZCTHRRzwm3k>).

LILIS^{zabar} *te-rim*,⁴³ (“You place 12 bronze gods inside the kettledrum and you cover the kettledrum”). Once the twelve⁴⁴ gods (in all likelihood, bronze figurines of them) had been placed inside (*a-na* ŠA₃) the *lilissu*, the drum had to be covered with its drumhead (*te-rim*) with no explicit order to remove the gods inside. IV R², 23-1+ is a Neo-Assyrian text and does not speak of “hands,” whereas the Late Babylonian text TU 47: obv. 16 mentions only nine “hands.” However, both texts are related to the same ritual (the covering of the *lilissu* with its drumhead)⁴⁵ and their wording is too similar not to consider them parallel descriptions of a similar reality. The “hands” of TU 47: obv. 16 could have represented the complete gods, which may have cross-cultural parallels, as a hand usually represent/symbolizes a whole person (e.g., when greeting someone).⁴⁶

As a second philological point to argue that the “hands” denoted by TU 47 were objects placed inside the *lilissu*, the texts that may suggest that the “hands” were placed outside the kettle of the *lilissu* describe something else. To prove this, I will comment on some lines from the first column in the reverse of TU 44, a Late Babylonian tablet from Uruk that constitutes the main account of the ritual to cover the *lilissu* with its drumhead.⁴⁷

- 24 *tu-še-pes-su* I₃.NUN.NA *u* I₃.ĜEŠ BARA₂.GE₂ ŠEŠ₂-*su* ^{[1]u^{2r}} GALA.MAḤ ŠU.MIN^{!?}
 25 *ana* UGU LI.LI.IS₃^{zabar} ŠUB-*di* KEŠ₂.MEŠ DU₈
 26 *ina* NIĜ₂.NA *u* GI.IZI.LA₂ *tu-ḥab-bi-šu*₂ ŠU.MIN LILIS *ana* IGI DIĜIR.ME
 27 DAB-*ma* *ina* ŠE.NUMUN.MEŠ GUB-*an*

- 24 You perform it (= the *mīs pî* ritual) on it (= the kettledrum). You anoint it (= the kettledrum) with butter and *pressed* sesame oil. The *kalamāḥu* will place the hands onto the top of the kettledrum. You clear away the ritual assemblages.
 25
 26 You purify it (= the kettledrum) with a censer and a torch. You lead the kettledrum to the
 27 gods and set (it) in (a bed of) barley seeds.

This excerpt appears in TU 44 once the *kalû* has covered the *lilissu* with its drumhead, and after an explanatory list naming twelve gods.⁴⁸ The first allusion to some hands occurs in lines rev. i 24–25. Previous research has proposed that these hands are those of the *lilissu*.⁴⁹ However, if the usual reading of ŠU.MIN^{!?} in rev. i 24 is certain,⁵⁰ TU 44: rev. i 24–25 reads ^{[1]u^{2r}} GALA.MAḤ ŠU.MIN^{!?} *ana* UGU LI.LI.IS₃^{zabar} ŠUB-*di*, not anything like *^{[1]u^{2r}} GALA.MAḤ ŠU.MIN^{!?} (*ša*₂) LI.LI.IS₃^{zabar} *ana* UGU-*šu* ŠUB-*di* (“The *kalamāḥu* will place the hands of the kettledrum on its top”). As ŠU.MIN^{!?} and LI.LI.IS₃^{zabar} would not be directly connected through a genitive construction, it could be argued that TU 44: rev. i 24 and TU 47: obv. 16 would use ŠU.MIN to describe different things.

Could TU 44: rev. i 24 refer to the hands of the *kalamāḥu* himself? If so, TU 44: rev. i 24–25 would prescribe him to beat the *lilissu*, making sure that the drumhead had been fastened correctly and that the ritual could continue. Testing is a key step in the fabrication of any musical instrument, but TU 44 does not refer to any testing of the *lilissu* before these lines. In favor of this proposal, the *kalamāḥu* would most probably test the sound

⁴³ Edition: Gabbay, *Pacifying the Hearts* (2014), 128 n. 450.

⁴⁴ This number of gods is also seen in the Late Babylonian texts BM 54119 = MacGinnis, “A cultic handlist?”; BTT, pl. 22: rev. ii 10’–15’; and TU 44: rev. i 1–14.

⁴⁵ On the continuities in this ritual from Neo-Assyrian to Late Babylonian times, see Linssen, *The Cults of Uruk* (2004), 96–97, 99–100.

⁴⁶ Alpenfels, “Anthropology and Social Significance of the Human Hand” (1955): 4, 19.

⁴⁷ Edition: CAMS/GKAB.

⁴⁸ TU 44: obv. ii 25, rev. i 1–14.

⁴⁹ Gabbay, *Pacifying the Hearts* (2014), 119 n. 368.

⁵⁰ Sadly, it was not possible to collate the tablet *in situ*.

of the *lilissu* by placing his hands on the drumhead. This is reminiscent of the chain *ana UGU.LI.LI.IS₃^{zabar} ŠUB* (“onto the top of the *lilissu*”) on TU 44.

If this proposal is accepted, one may wonder why it was the *kalamāhu*, and not the plain *kalû*, who tested the *lilissu*. There is no definitive answer for that, but note that the *kalamāhu* was the most experienced/skilled among the *kalû*-priests in a temple. Therefore, he could best detect any mistake in the fabrication of the *lilissu*.

Regarding the second allusion to ŠU.MIN in the sentence of TU 44: rev. i 26–27, scholars⁵¹ agree that we are in front of the expression ŠU.MIN ... DAB “to lead (something before someone)” with the led object (the *lilissu*) as the *nomen rectum* of ŠU.MIN.⁵² There would be, then, no allusion to the *kalû* holding (DAB) something placed outside the kettle of the *lilissu*. This understanding of TU 44: rev. i 26–27 may help to revisit another excerpt:

BM 73539. Obv.⁵³

3' [ER₂.ŠEM₃].MA *ana* ^dAMAR.UTU GIM ŠU.MIN *ša*₂ LI.LI.I[S₃^{zabar}? ...]
4' [...] ^rEN^r.MEŠ^r ^rŠA₃^r? E₂.KI.TUŠ.GAL.AN.NA D[AB^r? ...]

3' [Eršem]a prayer for Marduk, as soon as the hands of the kettledru[m ...]
4' [...] the lords (?) belonging to (?) the Ekitušgalanna temple [...]

The content of this text has been understood⁵⁴ as an allusion to the *modification* of the “hands” of the *lilissu* before the performance of the prayer mentioned in obv. 3', perhaps to tune the *lilissu*. However, the excerpt is badly preserved, so alternative interpretations are worth exploring. Perhaps ŠU.MIN *ša*₂ LI.LI.I[S₃^{zabar}? ...] is just a variant of ŠU.MIN ... DAB. If so, the *lilissu* could have been led to the gods of the Ekitušgalanna temple. In favor of this suggestion, what follows E₂.KI.TUŠ.GAL.AN.NA, according to the hand copy of this tablet,⁵⁵ might recall the shape of DIB (to be read DAB = *šabātu*) because of the position of its wedges. Notwithstanding, too little is preserved in this section of the tablet to confirm the suggested reading.

If the proposed identification of the “hands” mentioned by TU 47: obv. 16–20 as objects placed inside the *lilissu* is accepted, it is legitimate to ask about their role inside the kettle of the *lilissu*. The next section of this paper will try to answer this question.

6. The role of the “hands” inside the *lilissu*

In different cultures, the body of a cultic drum is filled with objects to extend its sound range (so that it can also be played as a rattle), or to help the drum acquire a particular sound.⁵⁶ There is no doubt that the “hands” would change the sound of the *lilissu*, perhaps muffling it partially. Nevertheless, these “hands” would not be the only tool of Mesopotamian people to change the sound of the *lilissu*. There are allusions to *lilissu*-kettledrums

⁵¹ Thureau-Dangin, *Rituel Accadiens* (1921), 17 and 52 (about n. 41); Pongratz-Leisten, *Ina šulmi īrub* (1994), 173; Gabbay, *Pacifying the Hearts* (2014), 171 n. 145. Sachs, “Akkadian Rituals” (1969), 335–336 might also align with such an understanding (“You shall grasp the “hand” of the kettle-drum (and bring it?) to the presence of the gods”). Linssen, *The Cults of Uruk* (2004), 258 and CAMS/GKAB seem to translate ŠU.MIN LILIS ... DAB more idiomatically into English as “to lead.”

⁵² Literally “to seize the hands of someone/something (to carry him/her/them/it to somewhere else).”

⁵³ Edition: Gabbay, *Eršema Prayers* (2015), 14.

⁵⁴ Gabbay, *Pacifying the Hearts* (2014), 119 n. 369 and 129 n. 458.

⁵⁵ Gabbay, *Eršema Prayers* (2015), plate 28. No photos of the tablet have been published yet.

⁵⁶ See below in the footnotes for some examples.

made of various metals.⁵⁷ At the same temperature, two pieces of different metals conduct the sound differently. Thus, Mesopotamian people could have obtained a specific type of sound from the *lilissu* just by fashioning it in a concrete type of metal (or an alloy of various metals). In any case, if the staff from a first-millennium Babylonian temple had wished to alter the sound of their *lilissu* specifically by introducing objects inside, one would have wanted to find other objects for such a purpose. In other cultures, bells or jingles are put inside a drum to increase its resonance.⁵⁸ When a drum is supposed to sound like a determined type of animal, parts of said animal (feathers, bones, part of an organ, etc.) are introduced inside the drum's body.⁵⁹ In the case of the *lilissu*, these parts should have come from a bull, as the *kalû*-priest asked the gods to confer the *lilissu* the sound of the bull, whose hide was used to fabricate the *lilissu*'s drumhead.⁶⁰ However, the closest thing to be currently documented is the use of the sinew from the bull's left thigh for fastening the drumhead to the kettle of the *lilissu*.⁶¹

As a result, placing "hands" inside the *lilissu* could have a rather non-musical purpose. The same applies to the dyeing of the *lilissu*'s drumhead. Dyes, and mordants used to fix these dyes, increase the thickness and reduce the elasticity of a drumhead. This lowers the pitch and reduces the resonance of a drum, as it reduces the number of harmonics produced by the drumhead.⁶² However, thanks to its red-dyed drumhead, the *lilissu* could also convey non-sonic messages related to the divine world.⁶³ This is consistent with the fact that the *lilissu* was closer to being a sounding statue⁶⁴ than a concert instrument.

What could be the non-sonic message to be conveyed by the "hands" inside the kettle of the *lilissu*? Various aspects in the accounts (e.g., TU 44) and commentaries (e.g., TU 47) of the ritual to cover the *lilissu* with its drumhead suggest that this ritual could have been understood in antiquity as a reflection of how Marduk killed the god Enmešara and his progeny after primordial strife for the rule of the universe.⁶⁵ For instance, the "hands,"

⁵⁷ Gold: Emar 6-1, p. 376: rev. ii' 5' (^{li-li-is}lilis ku₃-sig₁₇). Silver: UR₅-ra XII: Seg. 1, 189–190 (lilis ku₃-babbar). Allusions to *lilissu* of pure copper have a longer tradition: Textes Économiques 6055: obv. ii 9 and UTI 4, 2362: obv. 1 from the Ur III Period, the Old Babylonian text ARM 24, 105: obv. 2, and the Neo-Assyrian excerpts SAA 10, 347: obv. 9 and SAA 13, 12: rev. 13.

⁵⁸ Here we find the Indian wooden kettledrums filled with metal bells (*Sud.* τ.1164 = τύμπανα; edition: *Suda Online: Byzantine Lexicography*), and the Iberian *adufe*, whose wooden frame is filled with chickpeas and metal jingles (Molina, *Frame Drums* (2010), 140). In both cases, there is a material contrast unseen in the *lilissu*, whose kettle and "hands" would both be made of the same material: bronze.

⁵⁹ Blades, *Percussion instruments* (1984), 57–58. E.g., the body of the Kaluli drum from Papua New Guinea is filled with the feathers, tongue, and throat of a *pitohui* bird, so that the drum could sound like a *pitohui*. This ritual filling is preceded by the recitation of an invocation to ensure that the Kaluli drum gets the *pitohui*'s sound (Feld, "Sound as Symbolic System" (1986), 151–153).

⁶⁰ IV R², 23-1+: obv. i 25: [r]ⁱ-gimⁱ-š^u₂ ṭa-aⁱ-buⁱ a-na ^dEN liq-ṭa-'-iš, "may its sweet voice be offered to Bēl!" See Gabbay, "Drums, Hearts, Bulls" (2018): 13–14 for further comments.

⁶¹ KAR 60: rev. 9; TU 44: obv. ii 18, 30; BagM 2, 5: rev. 12.

⁶² This is, incidentally, why drumheads in concert drums are often left undyed. Thanks to the traditional drum makers Lev Elman and Ayoub al-Zaatari (through Marie Anell's mediation) for their insights.

⁶³ On the meaning of this red color, see Scurlock, "On Some Terms for Leatherworking" (2008), 173; Shehata, "Sounds from the Divine," (2014), 122; Thavapalan, *The Meaning of Color in Ancient Mesopotamia* (2019), 152 and Borrelli and Escobar, "Crafting Purity" (2022): 63–64.

⁶⁴ See Grame, "Sounding Statues" (1973): 30–39 for this concept. For instance, the *lilissu* had to receive offerings (just as any divine statue), according to TU 44: rev. i 16–18.

⁶⁵ Gabbay, "Drums, Hearts, Bulls" (2018): 25–31. These conclusions find support in newly published cuneiform texts and (unnoticed) cross-cultural parallels. Regarding the texts, see BM 38564: rev. 5, li-li-is₃ || ^dEn-me-š[ar₂-ra] as edited by eBL (<https://www.ebl.lmu.de/fragmentarium/BM.38564>). As for cross-cultural parallels, the *nagarā*-kettledrums from Nepal are covered with a bull hide that represents Mahiṣāsura, a demon killed by the Mother Goddess to restore heaven to the gods (Tingey, "Musical Instrument or Ritual Object" (1992), 105). Various late antique and medieval texts also compare the fastening of

or figurines, placed inside the *lilissu* were named according to the children of Enmešara and other gods defeated by Marduk.⁶⁶ Among these other deities, we find Šarur and Šargaz (mentioned by TU 47: obv. 19) and those listed alongside Enmešara's offspring in the cultic list of TU 44: rev. i 2–14: Anu, Enlil, and Ea,⁶⁷ with the possible inclusion of the pair of gods Lugal-Erra and Mes-lamta'ea.⁶⁸

In this context, one wonders whether placing the “hands” inside the kettle of the *lilissu* evoked how Marduk had sent Enmešara's offspring and allies to the Underworld. No other Mesopotamian ritual seems to use figurines in a fully similar manner,⁶⁹ and objects placed inside the body of ritual drums in various modern cultures are rather apotropaic and, therefore, stand for good, supernatural beings.⁷⁰ Nonetheless, there might be a parallel for this proposal about the *lilissu* and its “hands” in the case of the vessel drums in Native North America. Considered a representation of a multi-layered cosmos, the vessel of these ritual drums is filled with water to represent the waters of the Underworld.⁷¹

Is there evidence to argue that the *lilissu* could similarly, among other purposes,⁷² represent or map the structure of the universe? Nowadays, various shamanistic groups transform their drums into cosmic maps by making drawings on their drumheads.⁷³ However, the drumhead of the *lilissu* was dyed red, leaving little room to contain any (cosmic) depiction. Nevertheless, the pegs fastening the drumhead to the kettle of the *lilissu* could contribute to the perception of this kettledrum as a (multi-dimensional) cosmic map. TU 44: obv. ii 26–28 prescribes that the drumhead had to be fixed to the kettle of the *lilissu* with pegs from both native (ash and rosewood)⁷⁴ and foreign (sissoo, cedar, and ebony) trees in Mesopotamia. As a result, the wooden pegs could outline a cosmic map around the *lilissu*, arguably with the bottom of its kettle standing for the Underworld.

an animal hide over a wooden frame to make a frame drum (*tympanum*) and Jesus' flesh being nailed to the cross (Molina, *Frame Drums* (2010), 125–126; Günther, *Musik als Argument* (2019), 311–312).

⁶⁶ Bronze figurines archaeologically found in first-millennium Babylonian contexts often have an apotropaic character, but figurines of Lamaštu and other demons are also known (Braun-Holzinger, “Bronze Objects from Babylonia” (1988), 119, 121, 130 n. 1). Interestingly, severing the hands of enemy soldiers was an Ancient Egyptian military practice with Asiatic origins (Gresky, Julia, *et al.*, “First Osteological Evidence of Severed Hands in Ancient Egypt” (2023): 5239). Thanks to Roxana Flammini for this insight.

⁶⁷ Šarur and Šargaz referred to Ninurta's double-lion-mace emblem (Wiggermann, “BM 33055: A Late Babylonian Clay Tablet with Figures and Captions” (2018), 890). According to *Enmešara's Defeat*: obv. iii 12–15, 22, Marduk defeated to Ninurta, Anu, and Enlil. No allusions to Ea are preserved, but he was arguably defeated in this strife as well (Lambert, *Babylonian Creation Myths* (2013), 282, 292–293).

⁶⁸ TU 47: obv. 8–9 equates Lugal-Erra with Sîn, the first-born of Enlil (a god sent to the Underworld), and relates Mes-lamta-e'a to Nergal, the inhabitant of the Underworld (TUŠ KI-ti₃).

⁶⁹ As said by Debourse, *Of Priests and Kings* (2022), 255, “While in *Maqlû* and *Bīt rimki*, the figurines were destroyed in the course of the ritual, in *Bīt mēseri* they were thrown into the river at the end.”

⁷⁰ Venda people (Northern Transvaal, South Africa) place stones inside the *ngoma lungundu* drum that are supposed to come from the stomach of a crocodile, a totemic animal (Le Roux, “*Ngoma Lungundu*” (2009): 106). Some of the objects filling the shell of the Mapuche *kultrín* help the *machi*-priest(ess) to ward off evil beings (Pérez de Arce, *Instrumentos sonoros de Sudamérica* (2021), 372).

⁷¹ Rees, “Membrane Drums” (2013), 195–196.

⁷² SAA 3 39: obv. 11 compares the *lilissu* with the heart of a deity. TU 44: rev. i 17 and the reverse of TU 47 spell *lilissu* as ^dLILIS (lit. “divinized *lilissu*”), presenting it a complete entity of occasionally divine character. On the occasional deification of Mesopotamian sound tools (including the *lilissu*), see Hundley, “Divinized Instruments” (2023): 120–126.

⁷³ Hulkrantz, “Drum in shamanism” (1991): 16; Potapov, “Shaman's Drum” (1999): 26; Keski-Säntti, *et al.*, “Drum as Map” (2003): 122; Pentikäinen, “Shamanic drum as cognitive map” (2010).

⁷⁴ Pace Borrelli and Escobar “Crafting Purity” (2022): 64–65, rosewood (TAŠKARIN = *taskarinnu*) might no longer be a foreign tree in Mesopotamia by the first millennium BCE, the time in which the main texts describing the ritual to cover the *lilissu* with its drumhead (KAR 60, TU 44, and BagM 2, 5) were copied. Neo-Assyrian kings claim to have uprooted this tree in Babylonia (e.g., *Tiglath-pileser III* 47: obv. 24), planted it in Assyria (e.g., *Sennacherib* 16: viii 37–38), and used this wood to make some objects (e.g., *Sargon II* 7: 158). Thanks to Yuval Levavi for this insight.

Should this proposal (the kettle of the *lilissu* was filled with bronze figurines, recalling that Marduk had sent several gods to the Underworld in primeval times) be accepted, how were these “hands” perceived? After all, no one could see them. Fortunately, the Byzantine *Suda* might come to help on this matter, as it says that the bells placed inside the Indian τύμπανα produced a booming when the bodies of these drums were inclined and shaken.⁷⁵ Perhaps the “hands” inside the *lilissu* would be heard to some extent insofar as the *lilissu* was lifted from, and placed on, stands during a procession.

7. Conclusions

According to their main mention in the Late Babylonian text TU 47, the “hands” of the *lilissu* cannot denote handles, as their number (at least nine) would exceed the two handles shown in the Late Babylonian *lilissu* iconography (see Figure 1). These handles could be denoted by the Sumerogram ĜEŠTU (“ear”).

Identifying the “hands” with tuning bolts would overlook the system to fasten (and tune) the *lilissu*: glued pegs reinforced with a lace made of bull sinew. Nor should these “hands” be identified as drumsticks, because Mesopotamian iconography always depicts (kettle)drums played with the hands. This paper has proposed to compare the *lilissu* with kettledrums played with the hands, such as the *ḍuggī/bāyā* from Northern India.

The present contribution agrees with those studies (and translations of TU 47 and related texts) that see in the “hands” a designation of objects put inside the kettle of the *lilissu*. A reason for such an agreement is that there are no explicit orders to take the “hands” out of the *lilissu* after they have been placed inside. Additionally, those texts that could locate the “hands” outside the *lilissu* are actually denoting other hands. For instance, TU 44: rev. i 24–25 may denote the hands of the *kalamāḥu*, who would put his hands onto the top of the *lilissu* for testing its sound and ritual suitability.

As named according to the children and allies of Enmešara killed by Marduk during a primordial battle for the rule of the universe, these “hands,” or figurines made of bronze, would be put inside the *lilissu* to recall such primeval struggle. Therefore, the *lilissu* could have acted as a cosmic map, with the bottom of its kettle representing the Underworld. This article has argued that, for instance, the fastening pegs of the *lilissu*, made of native and foreign trees in Mesopotamia, would also portray the *lilissu* as a cosmic map.

Identifications of Sumerian and Akkadian musical terms tend to be quite volatile, and the ones made here will probably be no exception. In any case, this paper will have shown, at least, that the rich terminology for the parts of the Mesopotamian kettledrum (and perhaps other sound tools of the *kalû*-priest) should not be studied exclusively in sonic terms. A broader, perhaps polysensory or cultic, perspective should be adopted instead.

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⁷⁵ *Sud.* τ.1164 (= τύμπανα; edition: *Suda Online: Byzantine Lexicography*).

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